

SSHOC'n Tell Challenge

User Story

[View the presentation](#)

How to use VCR and Switchboard in teaching and training

Trying out

Iulianna van der Lek
CLARIN ERIC

Janna Besamusca
Universiteit Utrecht/
WageIndicator

Nanette Rißler-Pipka
GWDG, DARIAH ERIC

What

This challenge shows how the Virtual Collection Registry (VCR) and the Switchboard can be used in academic teaching and training, exploring the benefits for teachers, students and research infrastructures.

Who

We are researchers, teachers, and trainers in humanities and social sciences. We teach students and junior researchers to do research and interact with data, text corpora, and infrastructures for this purpose. Students can benefit from the VCR and Switchboard when they conduct research or work on assignments in teams, or when they search data or text collections offered by teachers. Scholars who do not use digital methods in their teaching may benefit from using these tools and enhance their digital skills too.

How

We teach students and other scholars how to use and consult collections and tools which are relevant to their research field (Literary studies, Linguistics, but also Social Sciences), such as data, texts, and training materials. The teachers and students also play an important role as testers/users and are able to provide valuable feedback for the further development of the tools.

- Teachers can use the Switchboard to encourage students to interact with the research infrastructure and try out different tools to process and analyse their data. Students can process a language dataset directly from the VLO, the TextGrid Repository or upload their own file. Switchboard automatically recognises the presented data/language and suggests a list of tools, software or web services that may be suited for processing the data.
- Experts can use the VCR to prepare specialised collections and share them with students or teachers to help them either in research or teaching. A VCR collection of existing training materials for the tools listed in the switchboard could be setup in order to help the teachers understand what the tools have to offer and which ones a resultable to integrate in their courses. Secondly, the VCR can be a tool where student teams make collections that are easily shared and citable.

When

The VCR and Switchboard tools can be used by teachers throughout the academic year, whenever an appropriate course is taught. The development of the tools towards more student-friendly operations should be synchronized with this process. We suggest teachers are invited to use and test the tools in their workflows and provide feedback about the further development.

Virtual Collection Registry

Switchboard

www.sshopencloud.eu

[@SSHOpenCloud](https://twitter.com/SSHOpenCloud)

[in/SSHOpenCloud](https://www.linkedin.com/company/SSHOpenCloud)

